

experiment. Treatments were a control and applications of urea, ammonium sulfate, and urea + S to equal 100 kg N and 120 kg S/ ha. The experiment was in a Latin square. Establishing the plots was not difficult because rice was planted in rows at equal spacing. The fertilizers were broadcast on the surface when the rice was 30 d old.

Three days after fertilizer application,

the rice plants in the ammonium sulfate treatment were distinctly darker green than in the urea treatment. Plants in the urea + S treatment turned green 7 d after application.

Three days after the problem was reported, it was identified and a solution was provided — applying 100 kg ammonium sulfate/ ha. The farmer saw how ammonium sulfate, compared with

other treatments, dramatically improved the growth and development of his rice plants. There was a need, however, to point out that it was the S in ammonium sulfate that solved the problem. Both ammonium sulfate and S significantly increased IR50 yield, and shortened the period to crop maturity (see table). *ℳ*

Response of rice to phosphorus application methods

S.K. Saggur, M.S. Maskina, and O.P. Meelu, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

We tested different methods of application to improve rice response to P fertilizer on light-textured soils. Soil was a loamy sand (Ustochrept) with pH 8.4, EC 0.20 mmho/cm, 0.23% organic C, and 6 kg Olsen's extractable P/ ha. Treatments were 13.1 kg P/ ha incorporated at last puddling, 13.1 kg P/ ha broadcast before transplanting, and a nursery root dip in 0.7% P slurry. N at 120 kg/ ha was applied in 3 equal

Effect of methods of P application on rice yield, Ludhiana, India.

splits and potash was applied at 13 kg K/ ha as a basal dose. Jaya seedlings aged 30 d were transplanted.

Grain yield was highest when P was incorporated at last puddling (see figure). Yields after the slurry treatment

were 150 kg/ ha less than the control, perhaps because of heat damage or chemical injury from the concentrated slurry. The slurry-treated plants wilted before transplanting and took more time than the normal seedlings to recover. *ℳ*

Effect of injured seedling roots on rice yield

M.S. Maskina, O.P. Meelu, and H.S. Baddesha, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Ludhiana 141004, India

Most rice grown in northern India is transplanted. Nurseries are grown using the wetland method. A fine, surface crust makes it difficult to uproot seedlings. Seedlings are uprooted manually, and because of the dense root mass and the crust, seedling roots often are damaged. Farmers think that root damage at transplanting reduces yields.

We studied the effect of seedling root damage on yields at the PAU Farm in 1982 and 1983. Treatments were:

- roots were handled carefully to avoid injury,
- roots were trimmed from the base of plants,
- 50% of the roots were removed, or
- all but 1 root was removed.

Effect of sodium, root injured on rice yield, Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ ha)	N uptake (kg/ ha)
All roots	5.9	78
Trimmed roots	5.6	70
50% roots	5.8	74
1 root	5.7	68

Thirty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted the second week of Jul. The crops received 120 kg N/ ha in equal splits at transplanting, 21 d after transplanting (DT), and 42 DT. PK at 13-12.5 kg/ ha were applied basally at transplanting. Soil was a loamy sand (Typic Ustochrept) with 5 mm percolation/ h, pH 8.5, EC 0.15 mmho/ cm, 0.23% organic C, and 0.06% total N.

Results (see table) showed that root injury did not affect grain yield. However, seedling N content and uptake were significantly lower when roots were trimmed at transplanting. *ℳ*

Yield response of IR32 to inorganic and organic fertilizers

R. le Cerff, R. Mufran, A. Buntan, and I. T. Corpuz, Maros Research Institute for Food Crops (MORIF), Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia

We studied the effect of applying NPKS as urea, TSP, KCl, and elemental S with rice straw, rice straw ash, rice hull ash, and carabao manure. Soil was a very fine, mixed, nonacid, isohyperthermic, alluvial Vertic Tropaquept. The surface 0-12 cm was clayey, with pH 6.5, 2.6% organic matter, 110 ppm available P (Olsen), CEC 32.0 meq/ 100 g, and 24.1,

IR32 grain yield as affected by NPKS, rice straw, carabao manure, rice straw ash, and rice hull ash application, South Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Treatment	Mean grain yield ^a (t/ha)
Control	2.4 b
NPKS	5.7 a
NPKS + rice straw	5.2 a
NPKS + carabao manure	5.1 a
NPKS + rice straw ash	5.8 a
NPKS + rice hull ash	5.6 a
Rice straw	2.7 b
Carabao manure	2.4 b
Rice straw ash	3.4 b
Rice hull ash	2.8 b
CV (%)	12.8

^aSeparation of means by DMRT at the 1% level.

5.6, and 0.8 meq exchangeable Ca, Mg, and K per 100 g.

NPKS rates were 120 kg urea, 25 kg TSP, 50 kg KCl, and 30 kg S/ha. N was applied 1/3 at planting and 2/3 5-7 d before panicle initiation. PKS were applied at planting. Six tonnes of rice straw or carabao manure/ha or 2 t rice straw ash or rice hull ash/ha were broadcast and incorporated just before planting. Treatments (see table) were in a randomized complete block design with four replications.

One month after planting, the rice plants in all the treatments that received NPKS alone or with straw, carabao

manure, straw ash, or hull ash were darker green, taller, and had more tillers than the control and the treatments without NPKS.

Applying rice straw, carabao manure, rice straw ash, or rice hull ash did not significantly increase yield (see table). *J*

ERRATUM

Y. Prasad and R. S. Singh. Screening for brown spot (BS) resistance in deep water rice. 10 (3) (Jun 85): 7.

In the table, change
 BKNFR2606-3-2-1-2 to
 BKNFR76026-3-2-1-2
 BKNFR76052-100-1-5-1 to
 BKNFR76029-100-1-5-1
 BKNFR76025-100-1-5-2 to
 BKNFR76029-100-1-5-2.

Announcements

New IRRI publications

The following new IRRI publications are available for purchase from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines:

Grain quality and marketing of rice

Impact of science on rice
Insights of outstanding farmers
Progress in upland rice research: proceedings of the 1985 Jakarta conference

Rice improvement in eastern, central, and southern Africa

Soil physics and rice. *J*

The International Rice Research Institute

P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines

Airmail